

Supplementary Information:

Empowering Ischemic Stroke Risk Assessment: A DNA-Based Lateral Flow Assay for miRNA-638 Detection

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1. Gold nanoparticle characterization

Fig. S1 Absorbance spectrum of synthesized AuNPs. Maximum absorbance peak is observed at 520 nm wavelength.

Fig. S2 TEM image of synthesized AuNPs.

2. Gold aggregation test

The Gold Aggregation Test (GAT), as described by Corday et al.,¹ is a crucial method employed to ascertain the optimal concentration of a probe (e.g. antibodies or DNA) for its conjugation onto the surface of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). This concentration represents the minimal amount of probe required to cover the maximum surface area of AuNPs. The addition of NaCl to the AuNPs induces their aggregation, leading to a distinctive colour transition from red to black. In the GAT procedure, varying concentrations of the probe are conjugated onto the AuNPs. Subsequently, a NaCl saturated solution is introduced to the conjugate. If the quantity of probe is insufficient to fully coat the surface of the AuNPs, the nanomaterial will undergo aggregation, resulting in a discernible change in the colour.

Fig. S3 Gold aggregation test applied on a capture DNA probe for miRNA-638.

Fig. S4 Absorbance spectra representation before and after the addition of 10 % (w/v) NaCl.

In our experiment (Fig. S3), we placed 150 μL of AuNPs and 10 μL of DNA probe at different concentrations in a 96 well-plate (DNA was previously treated with TCEP as explained in the main manuscript at section 2.5). The mixtures were left to rest for 10 minutes and then 10 μL of 10 % (w/v) NaCl were added. The colour changes can be observed immediately.

By conducting spectral measurements on various conjugates, both before and after the introduction of NaCl (Fig. S4), it becomes evident that the characteristic absorbance peak of AuNPs, typically observed at 520 nm (or 521 nm if they are conjugated), suffers an absorbance decrease when the DNA probe quantity is insufficient. Thus, the optimal probe concentration can be chosen by gauging this absorbance differential and selecting the concentration at which the decrease is minimal. In our study, we selected 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (equivalent to 0.012 mM) as optimal concentration of oligonucleotide through our measurements (Fig. S5).

Fig. S5 Absorbance decrease measured at 521 nm for different concentrations of DNA probe.

3. Other supporting data

Fig. S6 Linear ranges obtained after analysing the data acquired with A) PC scanner and ImageJ software
B) Immunochromato reader.

References

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2. J. M. Aran Perramon, A. Luque Gómez and J. Krupinski, Patent (EP3196317A1): Predictive methods of atherosclerosis and stenosis. Published online 2017.